

THE EVALUATION OF HIGH SCHOOL 12TH GRADE STUDENTS' OPINIONS ABOUT THE EFFECTIVENESS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION CLASSES

Özlem Zengin¹, Hayri Demir¹,
Fikret Alıncak², Uğur Abakay²ⁱ

¹Selçuk University, Faculty of Sport Sciences, Konya, Turkey

²Gaziantep University, Physical Education and Sport Department, Gaziantep, Turkey

Abstract:

The present study is conducted to identify 12th grade high school students' opinions about the effectiveness of physical education classes. In the study, the interview method of qualitative research method is used. In order to obtain data of the study, open-ended questions that are designed to evaluate students' views and suggestions are used. These questions are following: (1) How do you find the teaching of the lesson, (2) What are the achievements of the course, (3) What are popular and unpopular aspects of the lessons, (4) How do you relate these classes with other courses, (5) What are your recommendations in terms of how to do the class. The research group was formed with 50 students who are studying in the 12th grade in official high schools depending on Gaziantep Directorate of National Education. Content analysis is applied to the data obtained from student's opinions. Consequently, considering high school 12th grade students' opinions about physical education classes, it can be said that physical education classes are effective and efficient. It is identified that students think physical education classes are important as they contribute to the development of physical, psychological and social aspects of human beings. However, the number of class hours and environmental conditions are not sufficient enough so this affects the effectiveness of the classes negatively.

Keywords: high school, student, physical education, effectiveness

¹ Correspondence: email uabakay@gmail.com

1. Introduction

It is stated that physical activity has an important and effective role in human life and in the developmental process of the individual. It is seen as an important pillar and is scientifically effective. Physical Education and Sports activities not only help people socialize but also help the development of their psychomotor skills. Besides staying healthy through the physical education classes, individuals also keep themselves away from many bad habits (Mne, 2009; Alıncak, 2016a; Alıncak, 2016b). The effect of physical education activities on social development depends on having an active community of sports culture. Generally, beginning with schools, these types of activities increase the quality of life in society throughout the country. The purpose of the individual by carrying out such activities is to be comfortable in terms of health and bodily, applying what they learn in everyday life and to use the experience in a positive way (Mne, 2009).

Physical education includes all the activities carried out by providing individuals bodily and physical development to prepare them for the difficulties of daily life and have them build positive personalities as citizens (Erhan and Tamer, 2009). In order to have individuals be compatible with the developing technology, they should be brought up and educated with a strong will, as self-confident individuals who are open to innovation and development as well as teaching them to express themselves in effective manners. Physical education and sport help to a large extent with a person's development. To contribute in this way, the physical education should be given with an equipped and effective training (Canakay, 2006). Without any doubt, physical education gives myriad benefits in people's mental and physical development. In order to have physical education classes in an effective manner, it is important that program, teacher and student work together in a coordinated manner. These three features make the physical education classes eligible and effective. Therefore, the attitude and behavior of the students about the course is very important in terms of program and teachers (Karangil, 2006). Physical education and sports are a means of socialization and integration into society. Because physical education and sports are activities that protect the health of the individual, help them spend their free time in a healthy way, enable them fight against modern life's challenges more effectively and enrich their social relations. In this regard, it has a particular importance in elimination of problems arising with industrialization. In fact, one of the foremost goals of education is to find solutions to the problems posed by modern life. As it can be seen, in this regard physical education and sports are training elements (Baykoçak, 2002).

In secondary schools, physical education is taught compulsory in Grade 9 as 2 hours a week and in 10th, 11th and 12th grades the physical education classes are offered as elective classes 2 hours a week (ogm.meb.gov.tr, 2012). Physical education is an integral part of general education and aims the development of people's physical, mental, emotional and social trainings (Dauer and Pangraz, 1975; Bucher, 1983). In other words, physical education is preparing people for daily living conditions by ensuring their emotional and mental development (Kuru, 2000). According to Williams (1964) physical education is the whole physical activities that contribute to the development of the individual (physical, mental, emotional and social) and help him to have fun. According to Çöndü (1999), physical education activities are effective and important tools in getting rid of bad habits which cause addiction. In a study that is conducted with primary and secondary school students who are smoking, mostly students reported complaints about the hours of physical education classes and telling that they were not enough (Gökdemir and Kılınç, 2000).

The goal of physical education and sports in the educational institutions is to contribute to the development of people's awareness about healthy living. Therefore, schools should concentrate on sporting branches and activities that will contribute to individuals throughout their lives instead of competitive sports that are exhausting (Heipertz and Bohm, 1985). Physical education in general sense is related directly with individuals' health and personality development. When one's physical and intellectual development is in harmony, then the person may be more healthy, hardworking, peaceful and productive within the society at a higher level (Güçlü, 2001). Therefore, as physical education classes are effective in the development of children's emotional and mental aspects, they should be given more importance than other courses and must be taken into account (Şahin et al, 2001). In researches conducted with secondary school students, it is found that there are expectations on the acquisition of physical development and aesthetic beauty from physical education classes (Sunay and Sunay, 1996; Özdağ et al., 2006).

Secondary education consists of high schools that implement different programs, and students studying there find opportunities to study in one of these programs within their wills and capabilities. The constant development and changes in technology have serious impacts on people. In this process, the main task of education is to train individuals to be well equipped in return for its effect on the society. Equipped manpower is being physically, mentally and spiritually healthy. In order to have these features, an effective training that forms the basis of physical education and sports is needed. When sports concept is discussed with education, it should be included with physical education. The reason for this is that physical education and

sports complement each other and they are the integral parts of the whole. Thus, physical education and sports programs have an important place in the education process and program development (Çoban et al., 2003).

Physical education classes help people's development as an indispensable element of the school program. Through physical education and sports, individuals' physical development and psychomotor skills are enhanced and they also support children's cognitive, sensory and social development. In physical education classes, the first thing that should be aimed for is increasing child's level of knowledge about sports and they should be provided with knowledge on topics such as rules, techniques, and health nutrition (Çiçek et al., 2002). In achieving the objectives laid down for physical education and sports, no doubt that starting age in sports is as important as the age to start school. This includes the young person's age in sports or even performance age for some sports (between the ages of 14-18) moreover, at the end of this period when a young person is going to pursue vocational training at a university, physical education increases the value of his developmental characteristics in a healthy way (Sunay et al., 2002). In order to achieve the purpose of physical education classes in secondary schools via this application, they should be focused on athletic activities, fitness activities, health information and first aid, games, wrestling, folk dancing, and national ceremonial activities (Demirhan, 2006). While giving place to these activities in physical education classes at secondary schools the following applications should be considered (Açak et al., 1997; Aracı, 1999).

Considering the literature in the field, particularly in the development phase and high school term, the physical education classes and the scope of functioning of sporting events that are applied to students are very important. The present study is conducted to evaluate high school 12th grade students' opinions about the effectiveness of physical education classes and to reveal their views on the course process.

For this purpose, answers to the following questions are searched:

1. *What are the students' opinions in terms of how the physical education classes are done?*
2. *What are the opinions of the students in terms of attainments in the training classes?*
3. *What are popular and unpopular aspects of physical education classes?*
4. *What are students' opinions when physical education classes are associated with other classes?*
5. *What are your recommendations about how to do the classes?*

Method

In this part of the study, the information regarding the research model, research group, preparation and implementation of the measurement tool and the analysis of the data are given.

Research Model

A qualitative research model is used in the present research study. It is in the form of a case study design. Case study is a research design that examines facts in their life contexts. It is used in situations in which the boundaries of the fact and its environment are not clearly differentiated and when there are more evidences or data sources available (Yin, 1984; Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2006).

Compared to quantitative research methods, qualitative research methods offer more flexible opportunities and different approaches in analyzing issues and data collection methods to researchers. The main features of qualitative researches are: defining the problems (although it is not necessary to define the problem in the beginning of the study), studying environmental factors within the frame of the participants, obtaining the data from a selected small group, and using interpretive approaches to reach descriptive stories of the participants and their environment instead of using numerical approaches (Gay et al., 2006).

Research Group

The study is conducted with 50 12th grade students who were studying in government high schools of Gaziantep Province. The data related to the research group is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: School Type and Gender Features of the Research Group

Variables	Groups	N	%
	Science High School	10	20
	Anatolian High School	10	20
	Religious Vocational High School	10	20
SCHOOL TYPE	Girls High School	10	20
	Vocational High School	10	20
	Total	50	100

	Girls	26	52
GENDER	Boys	24	48
	Total	50	100

Preparation and Implementation of the Measuring Tool (Interview Form)

In order to establish the interview form to be used in the study, primarily interviews are conducted with 130 high school students. These 12th grade high school students are asked to write essays about their views on the effectiveness of physical education courses. As a result of the information obtained via essays and literature, the interview form is prepared. The views of experts in the field are asked in order to determine the validity of the interview form. One of the logical paths that are used to test content validity is asking expert opinion (Büyüköztürk, 2006). The necessary corrections are made in accordance with the interviews, and the interview form is shaped, comprised of 2 questions that determine personal characteristics and 5 open-ended questions. Students can use more than one expression while they are answering open-ended questions. Each expression that is related to the program has been identified as a theme. The data is gathered via applying the interview form from 50 students who 12th grade students were volunteering to participate in the study who was attending high schools in the province of Gaziantep. The goal of the research is explained to the students so that they will understand the importance of their answers to the questions asked in the form.

Data Analysis

The data obtained from the interviews were analyzed using content analysis method which is used in qualitative researches (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2006). In contrast to quantitative researches like some other studies (Abakay, 2013; Polat et al., 2011; Özdal, 2016a; Özdal, 2016b, Bilgiç et al., 2016; Cinpolat et al., 2016; Yıkılmaz et al., 2015), the content analysis is used in themes that are not theoretically certain and in the analysis of establishing sub-themes if there are any, in qualitative researches (Alıncak, 2016b). The collected data is recorded and grouped for each question and separately coded. These grouping and codings are presented to experts for expert opinion, and depending on their evaluations, final editions of the forms were prepared for the analysis. When starting to analyze, themes are identified for each question and the frequencies and percentages of the themes were calculated and the tables were formed. In the evaluation of the data descriptive analysis is used. Finally, the reporting is completed and the results are presented.

Findings

In this part, the findings that are obtained from the interviews that are carried out with the research group are included.

Table 2: The Distribution of the Opinions of Research Group About how the Physical Education Classes Were Done

Themes	n	%
The classes are enjoyable and fun	24	22.5
The hours of the classes should be increased	22	20.5
Physical and environmental conditions are poor	18	16.9
Different activities should be done	16	14.9
The classes should be generally given as in applied classes	10	9.4
The classes should be valued	6	5.6
We learned new subjects	6	5.6
The classes are physically and spiritually relaxing	5	4.6
Total	107	100

In Table 2 the distribution of the opinions are given regarding the research group about how the physical education classes are done. From the opinions of the participants, eight themes have emerged regarding physical education classes. It is seen that the participants expressed multiple themes. According to the percentile rankings, four themes come to the fore from these eight themes and these are as follows: the classes are enjoyable and fun (22.5%), the hours of the classes should be increased (20.5%), physical and environmental conditions are not adequate (16.9%), different activities should be performed (14.9%).

Table 3: The Distribution of the Opinions of the Research Group about the Attainments in Physical Education Classes

Themes	n	%
We learned new information	22	21.4
We loved sports	20	19.5
Our skills are discovered	16	15.5

We are more conscious about healthy living	13	12.7
The classes helped us socialize	12	11.6
The activities are inadequate	8	7.7
We learned about the new sports branches	6	5.8
We learned nothing	6	5.8
Total	103	100

In Table 3 the opinions of the attainments of the research group in the physical education classes are given. From the opinions of the participants about the attainments of the physical education classes eight themes emerged. It is seen that the participants have expressed multiple themes. According to the percentile rankings five themes come to the fore from these eight themes and these are as follows: we learned new information (21.4%), we loved sports (19.5%), our skills are discovered (15.5%), we are more conscious about healthy living (12.7%) and the classes helped us socialize (11.6%).

Table 4: The Distribution of the Opinions of the Research Group about the Popular and Unpopular Aspects of the Physical Education Classes

Themes	n	%
The classes are enjoyable and fun	24	19.8
The hours of the classes should be increased	22	18.2
It is a great course in all aspects	21	17.3
I love the course	16	13.2
It is a necessary and important course	13	10.8
It is a great course to rest	11	9.1
Students shouldn't see it as a class without teacher	8	6.6
The course should be valued	6	5
Total	121	100

In Table 4 the distribution of popular and unpopular aspects of the research group regarding physical education classes is presented. From the participants opinions about popular and unpopular aspects of the physical education classes 8 themes emerged. It is seen that participants expressed multiple themes. According to the percentile rankings

six themes come to the fore and these are as follows: a very enjoyable and fun course (19.8%), the hours of the classes should be increased (18.2%), a great course in all aspects (17.3%), I love the course (13.2%), it is a necessary and important course (10.8%) and it is a great course to rest (9.1%).

Table 5: The Distribution of the Opinions about Physical Education Course when Associated With Other Courses Taken by Subjects of the Research Group

Themes	n	%
It is more enjoyable and fun compared to other classes	42	40.8
The hours of physical education classes should be increased	22	21.3
All the grades should have physical education classes	18	17.5
Physical Education course is necessary and important	18	17.5
The course has no meaning	3	2.9
Total	103	100

The opinions of the research group when physical education course is associated with other courses are presented in Table 5. When physical education courses are associated with other courses, five themes emerged from the opinions of the participants. It is seen that participants expressed multiple themes. According to the percentile rankings four themes come to the fore and these are as follows: physical education course is a very enjoyable and fun course compared to other courses (40.8%), the hours of the classes should be increased (21.3%), the physical education classes should be given in all grades (17.5%), and it is a necessary and important course (17.5%).

Table 6: The Distribution of the Data Regarding the Recommendations of the Research Group about How the Physical Education Classes Should Be Done

Themes	n	%
The hours of physical education classes should be increased	25	22.1
There should be different activities	22	19.4
The number of the activities should be increased	20	17.7
Physical and environmental conditions should be taken care of	13	11.5
Students should be supported in terms of their skills	11	9.7
The students should be encouraged to do sports	10	8.8

The course should be valued	6	5.4
The classes should be generally given as in applied classes	6	5.4
Total	113	100

Table 6 gives the distribution of the data regarding the recommendations of the research group about how the physical education classes should be done. There are eight emerging themes from the opinions of the participants in terms of how the physical education classes are done. It is seen that participants expressed multiple themes. According to the percentile rankings eight themes come to the fore and these are as follows: the hours of the classes should be increased (22.1%), there should be different activities (19.4%), the number of the activities should be increased (17.7%), the physical and environmental conditions should be taken care of (11.5%), the students should be supported in terms of their skills (9.7%) students should be encouraged to do sports (8.8%), the physical education course should be valued (5.4%).

Conclusion

In this part of the study, the results are given which are obtained from 12th grade students' interviews. The study has been conducted in order to find out how the physical education course is applied in public schools and to review its effectiveness.

When the results regarding the opinions of the research group in terms of how the physical education classes are done the following is seen: 24 students expressed that the course is enjoyable and fun, 22 of them expressed that the hours of the classes should be increased and 18 of them expressed that physical and environmental conditions are poor and different activities should be done. In addition, they expressed that the classes should generally be given as applied classes, the course should be valued, and they learned new subjects and the classes are physically and spiritually relaxing. As it can be understood from the results, it can be said that the physical education classes are generally interesting and popular so there is a productiveness resulting from students' willingness, but that more importance should be given to the course.

When the distribution of the opinions regarding the attainments of physical education classes are examined the results are as follows: 22 students gained new information in the classes, 20 students loved sports because of the physical education classes, 16 students expressed that their skills are discovered, 13 students were more conscious about healthy living and 12 of them stated that the classes helped them to

socialize. While 8 students were expressing that the activities were inadequate, 6 of them expressed that they didn't learn anything. When the results obtained are evaluated, it can be said that physical education classes contribute to students having new information about healthy living and sports. It can also be said that students loved sports, and their socialization process within the society quickened with the help of the physical education classes. Additionally, personal characteristics such as working together and obeying rules were developed.

When the opinions of the research group about the aspects of physical education classes being popular and unpopular, the following was observed: 24 students expressed that the classes are very enjoyable and fun, 22 students expresses that the hours of the classes should be increased and 21 students stated that physical education classes are great in every aspects. In addition, 16 students expressed that they loved the course, 13 of them find the course necessary and important and 8 students expressed that the course is an ideal course to rest. Therefore, it can be said that students showed interest in their physical education course in terms of their own physical needs, and that they loved the course. When the opinions of the research group are examined in terms of the association between physical education course and other courses, most of the students stated that the physical education courses are enjoyable and fun. In addition, 22 students expressed that the hours of the classes should be increased, 18 students expressed that physical education classes should be in all grades and 18 students have also expressed the opinion that the course is necessary and important. Hence, it can be said that physical education classes should be given in all grades and the hours of the classes should be increased so that students can be removed from bad habits.

When students' recommendations are examined in terms of how the physical education classes are done, most of them have indicated the need to increase the class hours of the physical education course and there should also be different activities and the numbers of the activities should be increased, the physical and environmental conditions should be improved, students should be supported in terms of their ability, students should be encouraged to do sports, the course should be valued and the course should be given as in applied classes.

Abakay et al (2015) conducted a study with teachers on the physical education and sport classes in secondary school it is found that most of the teachers found the program insufficient in terms of some features (programs, physical conditions, student characteristics, course hours, environmental conditions).

When studies conducted with secondary school students are examined, it is seen that secondary school students' attitudes and behaviors are positive in terms of physical education courses (Chung and Philips., 2002; Hatten., 2004; Koca and Aşçı., 2004; Koca

and Demirhan., 2004; Alenezi., 2005; Balyan et al., 2005; Koca et al., 2005; Koca and Aşçı., 2006). Alıncak et al (2016). conducted a study with high school physical education and sports teachers and found that to have the classes effective and efficient, the following issues should be taken into consideration: the equipment that is used in the class, the physical conditions, an increase in the teaching hours, giving importance to the course and that the classes should lead the students to be more productive.

Consequently, depending on the opinions of the 12th grade high school students about physical education classes, it can be said that physical education classes are effective and efficient. The students think that physical education course is an important lesson that contributes to developing the human being physically, psychologically and socially. However, factors such as lack of class hours and lack of environmental conditions are affecting the effectiveness of the course negatively.

References

1. Abakay, U. (2013). Investigating physical education teacher candidates' epistemological beliefs. *Life Science Journal*, 10(3), 2658-2664.
2. Abakay, U., Alıncak, F., Akyel, Y., Yetiş, Ü. (2015). The evaluation of teachers' opinions about physical education secondary and sports classes. *Route Educational and Social Science Journal*, 2(4), 1-9.
3. Açak, M., Ilgın, A., Erhan, S. (1997). *Handbook of Physical Education Teachers*. Malatya: Sezer Ofset. p:11,12
4. Alenezi, M.A. (2005). *Attitude of Secondary Students toward Physical Education Classes in Kuwait*. Ph.D. Thesis, The Pennsylvania State University. p:5,227.
1. Alıncak, F. (2016a). Attitudes of secondary school students including physical activity involving playing games. *European Journal of Physical Education and Sport Science*, 2(3), 1-14.
5. Alıncak, F. (2016b). Evaluation of opinions of primary school teachers on the method of education with game. *European Journal of Physical Education and Sport Science*, 2(3), 82-96.
6. Alıncak, F., Doğan, İ., Abakay, U. (2016). Evaluation of teachers' opinions about high school physical education and sports classes. *Route Educational and Social Science Journal* Volume 3(1):309-317.
7. Aracı, H. (1999). *Physical Education in Schools*. (Second Edition). Ankara: Bağırgan Publisher. p:3,28-32. Ankara: Bağırgan

8. Balyan, M., Moralı, S., Onursal, A.M. (2005). The attitudes of various secondary school students toward physical education lessons (İzmir Sample). 46th ICHPER-SD Anniversary World Congress, November 9-13, Grand Cevahir Hotel and Convention Center, İstanbul. p:194,195.
9. Baykoçak, C. (2002). Physical Education Teachers' Professional Issues and Burnout Levels (Application in the province of Bursa). Unpublished Master's Thesis, Ankara University Institute of Social Sciences, Sakarya.
10. Bilgiç, M., Biçer, M., Özdal, M. (2016). Farklı branşlarda spor yapan 11-13 yaş grubu çocukların 2D:4D parmak oranlarının sportif performansla ilişkisinin incelenmesi. *Gaziantep Üniversitesi Spor Bilimleri Dergisi*, 1(1), 48-56.
11. Bucher, A. C. (1983). *Foundations of Physical Education & Sport*. London: The C.V. Mosby Company. 13.
12. Büyük Öztürk, Ş. (2006). *Data analysis for the social sciences*. Ankara: PegemA.
13. Canakay, E.U. (2006). Developing an attitude scale towards music theory course, *The National Music Education Symposium*.
14. Chung, M., Philips, D.A. (2002). Attitude toward physical education and leisure-time exercise in high school students. *Physical Educator*, 59, (3), 126-139.
15. Çiçek, S., Koçak, S., Kirazcı, S. (2002). The importance and the frequency of students' participation in physical education classes depending on the effect of various teacher and student behaviors. *Gazi Journal of Physical Education and Sports Sciences*, VII (4), 3-14.
16. Cinpolat, T., Alıncak, F., Abakay, U. (2016). Beden eğitimi ve spor yüksekokulu öğrencilerinin öğretmenlik mesleğine yönelik tutumlarının incelenmesi. *Gaziantep Üniversitesi Spor Bilimleri Dergisi*, 1(1), 38-47.
17. Çoban, B., Devecioğlu, S., Sarıkaya, M., Güler, G., Zirek, O., Turan, M. (2003). A study on the reasons of why the classes in sports field are not opened secondary education. *Ankara Gazi University School of Physical Education and Sports, Physical Education and Social Studies in Sport Conference*. 10-11,102-109.
18. Çöndü, A. (1999). *Special Teaching Methods in Physical Education and Sports*. Ankara: Nobel Publications. p:1-4,21.
19. Dauer, V.P. and Pangrazi, R. P. (1975). *Dynamic Physical Education For Elementary School Children*. (Fifth Edition). Minnesota: Burgess Publishing Company. s:2.
20. Demirhan, G. (2006). *Fundamentals of Sports Training*. Ankara: Bağırhan Publications. p:15.
21. Erhan, S.E., Tamer, K. (2009). The relations between the facility-tool conditions that is necessary in physical education classes in primary and secondary school

- that are located in the East Anatolian region and the attitudes of students towards physical education classes.
22. Gay, L., Mills, G., Airasian, P. (2006). Educational research: Competencies for Analysis and Application (8th ed.). New York: Prentice Hall.
 23. Gökdemir, K., Kılınç, F. (2000). The effect of physical education and sports on some primary and secondary school students' smoking habits. Physical Education and Sports Science Congress. (Volume I). 26th-27th May, Ankara. P: 180
 24. Güçlü, M. (2001). Development of Physical Education and Sports in Europe, The United States, China and Turkey, National Education Journal p:33,38-150.
 25. Hatten, J.D. (2004). Racial Differences in Student's interest and Attitudes Toward Physical Education Considering Grade Level and Gender. Ph.D Thesis. The Florida State University. p:52,53.
 26. Heipertz, W., Böhmer, D. (1985). Sports Medicine. Kırklareli: Sermet Press.
 27. http://ogm.meb.gov.tr/meb_iys_dosyalar/2012_09/05092630_ogmhd20122013.pdf / 06.09.2012
 28. Karangil, M., Hünük, D., Demirhan, G. (2006) The comparison of elementary, high school and university students' attitudes towards physical education and sports, Journl of Sports Sciences, 17 (2), 48 57
 29. Koca, C., Aşçı, F.H., Demirhan, G. (2005). Attitudes toward physical education and class preferences of Turkish adolescents in terms of school gender composition. Adolescence, 40, (158), p:365-373.
 30. Koca, C., Aşçı, F.H. (2004). Athletic proficiency level and the effect of gender on attitudes towards physical education. Gazi Physical Education and Sports Journal, IX, (1), p:15-24.
 31. Koca, C., Aşçı, F.H. (2006). An examination of self-presentational concern of turkish adolescents: an example of physical education setting. Adolescence, 41, (161), p:185-197.
 32. Koca, C., Demirhan, G. (2004). An examination of high school students' attitudes toward physical education with regard to sex and sport participation. Perceptual & Motor Skills, 98, (3), 754-758.
 33. Kuru, E. (2000). Program Development in Physical Education and Sports. Ankara: 4th Evening Art School Press.
 34. General Directorate of Secondary Education of Ministry Secondary School Physical Education Curriculum (9th- 12th grades) National Education 2009 Bursa
 35. Özdağ, S., Kürkçü, R., Kılınç, M. (2006). High school students' expectations from physical education classes in terms of their school diversity and the realization

- levels of their expectation levels. 9th International Sports Science Congress. November 3rd-5th, Atatürk Cultural Center, Muğla. p:274.
36. Özdal, M. (2016a). Acute effects of inspiratory muscle warm-up on pulmonary function in healthy subjects. *Respiratory Physiology & Neurobiology*, 227; 23-26.
 37. Özdal, M. (2016b). Influence of an eight-week core strength training program on respiratory muscle fatigue following incremental exercise. *Isokinetics and Exercise Science*, 24, 225-230.
 38. Polat, Y., Biçer, M., Patlar, S., Akıl, M., Günay, M., Çelenk, Ç. (2011). Examination on the anthropometric features and somatotypes of the male children at the age of 16. *Science & Sports*, 26(3), 150-156.
 39. Sunay, H., Gündüz, N., Tanılkan, K. (2002). A study on the achievement levels and priorities of the objectives regarding physical education and sports classes that are applied in secondary education institutions. *Gazi Physical Education and Sports Sciences Journal*, VII, (3), p:35-52.
 40. Sunay, Y., Sunay, H. (1996). High school students' expectations from physical education and the realization level of these expectations. *Journal of Physical Education and Sports Sciences*, I, (4), p:35-53.
 41. Şahin, M., Pehlivan, Z., Kuter, F. Ö. (2001). Ethic problems that occur in physical education class applications and their solution suggestions. II. National Physical and Sports Teaching Symposium, 21st-23rd December, Bursa. p:71.
 42. Williams, J. F. (1964). *The Principles of Physical Education*. London: W.B. Saunders Company. p:13
 43. Yıkılmaz, A., Biçer, M., Gürkan, A.C., & Özdal, M. (2015). The evaluation of physical fitness of the primary and secondary schools students in 8-12 age group related to the performance. *Beden Eğitimi ve Spor Bilimleri Dergisi*, 9, 300-307.
 44. Yıldırım, A., Şimşek, H. (2006). *Qualitative research methods in the social sciences*. (6th edition) Ankara: Seçkin.
 45. Yin, R.K. (1984). *Case study research: Design and methods*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Authors will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Physical Education and Sport Science shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflict of interests, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated on the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).